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Editorial

Drinking Milk Behavior and Bone Health among the Elderly

fracture can bring heavy burden to the society and family. Few drugs can treat osteoporosis, and there is no standard treatment of osteoporosis. Hence, early detection of risk factors for osteoporosis and high-risk groups, and early intervention to prevent the occurrence of osteoporosis has important significances. Studies have shown that vitamin D, calcium and protein for bone reconstruction, maintain bone salt content; reduce the risk of fracture [4-6]. Studies have shown that drinking milk can reduce bone loss. Because of estrogen, postmenopausal women are easy to bone loss, therefore, it's very important for postmenopausal women to drink milk [7].

Further research need to explore the behavioral effects on bone health, provide the correct scientific idea, and correct some errors in the current news reports. It is important to promote healthy behaviors to the whole society, especially to increase the understanding of the benefits of drink milk. Future measures on the prevention osteoporosis should promote a lifestyle (Good psychological, reasonable nutrition and proper exercise) for the elderly.

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Editorial

WHO report that in 2002 there were an estimated 605 million older persons in the world, nearly 400 million of whom were living in low-income countries, by 2025, the number of older persons worldwide is expected to reach more than 1.2 billion, with about 840 million of those in low-income countries [1]. WHO report that worldwide estimates are that 9.6% of men and 18.0% of women aged over 60 years have symptomatic osteoarthritis? 80% of those with osteoarthritis will have limitations in movement, and 25% cannot perform their major daily activities of life [2]. With the accelerating aging process, incidence of osteoporosis is increasing rapidly.

The elderly are easy to get calcium deficiency diseases such as osteoporosis, bone hyperplasia. The elderly have poor digestion and absorption function reduce the absorption of calcium, lack of exercise and insufficient dietary calcium. The long-term insufficient intake of calcium has become a major cause of bone health problem. Adequate intakes of calcium (500 mg per day or more) and of vitamin D in populations with high osteoporosis rates helps to reduce fracture risk, so does sun exposure and physical activity to strengthen bones and muscles. Research in Shanghai shows that 62.3% of the elderly has bad dairy consumption behavior, the cause of the elderly does not eat dairy products mainly include: terrible taste, economic reasons and physical discomfort after eating [3]. Therefore, promote the diet and exercise is an important content of the elderly care.

Osteoporosis is one of the most common diseases of the elderly and its prevention and control are very important. The osteoporosis

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